

PROTOCOL — SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW

1. Research Project Information

Public Title:

Explainability Practices and Challenges from the Experience of a Brazilian Industrial Research and Innovation Company

Principal Investigator:

[Omitted for double-blind review]

Advisor:

[Omitted for double-blind review]

Contact:

[Omitted for double-blind review]

Ethics Approval:

Approved by a Research Ethics Committee of a higher education institution in Brazil.

2. Interview Script

Each interviewee receives a copy of the interview guide to follow the questions and facilitate understanding. For remote participants, the guide may also be shared on screen.

The purpose of the interview is to investigate how explainability is perceived and applied in Requirements Engineering (RE) for Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based systems. The study aims to understand practices, challenges, quality attributes, and trade-offs involved in integrating explainability.

The interview is divided into four parts:

1. Participant profile
2. AI project characterization
3. Explainability and RE practices
4. Challenges and needs

Part 1 – Participants' Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Current workplace: Please select the option that best describes your organization:
 Industry
 University / Innovation hub / Research center
 Other: _____
3. Country of work: _____

4. Which of the following best describes your experience with AI projects?
- I have at least two years of experience working on ML projects
 - I am currently working on an ML project or have worked on one in the past two years
5. Experience with RE:
- No experience; I have never worked with Requirements Engineering
 - < 1 year
 - 1–5 years
 - 6–10 years
 - > 10 years

Part 2 – Characterization of AI Projects

Before the interview, the participant agreed on which project would be discussed. Thus, the conversation focused on a project that had some relation to the explainability requirement. Even in cases where explainability was not explicitly considered during the project development, the interviewee was invited to report whether this aspect had any impact on the project.

6. How were the ML-based systems delivered? Please select the option(s) that best describe the stage of system delivery or development
- Fully developed and approved operational system, successfully deployed
 - Fully developed and approved operational system
 - Prototype system or subsystem demonstration in an operational environment
 - Prototype system or subsystem demonstration in a relevant environment
 - Verification of critical function of component and/or subsystem in a relevant environment
 - Functional verification of component and/or subsystem in a laboratory environment
 - Proof of concept
 - Concept and/or technology application formulated
 - Basic principles observed and reported
7. What is the application domain of this project? Please select the option(s) that best apply:
- Healthcare
 - Agribusiness
 - Financial
 - Automotive
 - Manufacturing
 - Education
 - E-commerce
 - Logistics and transportation
 - Security and defense

- Energy
- Entertainment and media
- Environment and sustainability
- Legal and compliance
- Telecommunications
- Other: _____

8. Which ML tasks were addressed in the project(s)?

- Prediction
- Image recognition
- Recommender systems
- Robot navigation
- Classification
- Anomaly detection
- Natural language processing
- Machine translation
- Speech recognition
- Sentiment analysis
- Route planning or optimization
- Other: _____

9. Was there a Requirements Engineering (RE) specialist on your team?

- Yes:
 - Role of this person in the team: _____
 - Education or experience in RE: _____
- No

Part 3 – RE Practices for Explainability

Before starting this section, the participant was informed about the concept of the explainability requirement and the perspective from which we sought their perception.

10. In the ML projects you have been or are currently involved in, was there any concern regarding the explainability requirement?

- Yes
- No

11. If **YES** (linked to question 10):

How was this concern addressed? Was there a specific process? If so, what was it? Was someone on the team responsible for it? Were any specific tools or techniques used? Which ones?

12. If **NO** (linked to question 10):

What were the reasons explainability was not a concern?

- High financial cost
- Time-consuming
- Project coordinator lacked knowledge

- Team lacked knowledge
- Explainability was not a priority in the project context
- Other: _____

Next steps based on response to question 10:

- If YES: answer question 11, and then we will continue discussing aspects of RE.
- If NO: answer questions 15, 17, and 22, and proceed to the section on challenges and needs related to explainability.

Elicitation (YES – related to question 10)

Requirements Engineering is a discipline that encompasses several essential activities for software development.

The first activity is requirements elicitation, which aims to identify and understand the needs of the client or user that the software must meet (SWEBOK, v.4). This stage is crucial to ensure that expectations are clear and aligned with the project's objectives.

Note: all questions in this section refer to explainability.

13. Which elicitation techniques do you use or have you used to identify requirements related to explainability in ML projects?

- Interview
- Brainstorming
- Analysis of technical documentation, laws, and regulations
- Mind mapping
- Prototyping
- Reverse engineering
- Reuse of artifacts/documentation
- Scenarios
- Questionnaires
- Observation
- Analysis of competing systems
- Others: _____

14. What are the main sources for eliciting explainability-related requirements in ML projects?

- Users
- Clients
- Technical documentation, laws, and regulations
- Scientific papers and/or books
- Memos, meeting minutes, contracts
- Similar products
- Development team members
- Others: _____

Question 15 can be answered independently of Question 11.

15. Which stakeholders do you consider most relevant for providing information about the need for explainability? Please rank the stakeholders below, from least relevant (1) to most relevant (5). You may repeat the same number if applicable.

- Data scientist
- Project manager
- Domain expert
- End user
- Requirements engineer
- Business analyst
- Machine learning engineer
- Business owner(s)
- Others (add as many as you wish): _____

Analysis (YES – related to question 10)

The second activity is requirements analysis.

This stage helps developers understand the meaning and implications of the requirements identified during elicitation. For example, it involves assessing the feasibility of each requirement, considering whether it can be implemented in a practical and cost-effective way, taking into account factors such as budget, schedule, team, and other constraints (SWEBOK, v. 4).

16. Which analysis techniques are used when dealing with the explainability requirement? Below are some possible techniques. Please check those used in your process or add others you apply:

- Grouping — organizing similar explainability requirements to facilitate analysis and treatment
- Prioritization — defining which explainability requirements should be addressed first, based on their importance to the project (e.g., release planning)
- Requirements classification — classifying explainability requirements into types, such as functional (what explainability must do to support a function), non-functional (quality attributes such as performance and explainability), or data-related requirements
- Modeling — transforming explainability requirements into graphical representations or other models that help visualize them more effectively
- Other techniques you use: _____
- I do not use any analysis technique

If the interviewee mentions “modeling” in the previous question:

What types of diagrams or artifacts are used/generated to model explainability requirements?

- Use case diagram
- Flowchart
- Activity/Swimlane diagram
- ER diagram (Entity-Relationship)

- State machine diagram
- Class diagram
- BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation)
- Others: _____

Question 17 can be answered independently of Question 11.

17. How do you analyze explainability to identify conflicts, dependencies, or implications in relation to other requirements, such as transparency, traceability, reliability, and ethics?

Specification (YES – related to question 10)

The third stage is requirements specification. At this point, the requirements have already been defined, and it is essential to document them clearly and systematically, ensuring they can be easily communicated, tracked, and managed throughout the development process.

18. Do you use any specification document to define explainability needs for different stakeholders?
19. Which specification techniques do you use when defining explainability requirements? (Check all that apply.)
- Conversation flow
 - User story
 - Natural language
 - Modeling
 - User interface mockups
 - Formulas, metrics, or mathematical measures
 - Use case specification
 - Scenarios
 - Table
 - Others: _____
20. Which attributes do you use to define an explainability requirement? (Consider, for example, aspects related to clarity, traceability, and contextual relevance of the requirement.)
- Justification (why the requirement is important)
 - Relationship with other requirements (e.g., a functionality that needs to be explainable)
 - Classification (data requirements, functional requirements, non-functional requirements, etc.)
 - Others: _____

Validation (YES – related to question 10)

The validation activity corresponds to the 4th stage of Requirements Engineering. The goal is to verify whether the client's requirements have actually been met.

21. Which techniques do you use for validating and verifying explainability requirements?

- Acceptance test scenarios
- Inspection (i.e., formal review of requirements by stakeholders)
- Peer review (feedback from one or more engineers)
- Prototyping
- Simulation
- Other: _____

Question 22 can be answered independently of Question 11.

22. With which stakeholders are or can the explainability requirements be validated?

- Data analyst
- Data scientist
- Project coordinator
- Domain expert
- End user
- Requirements engineer
- Business analyst
- Machine learning engineer
- Business owners
- Others: _____

Management

Requirements management consists of ensuring that the scope of the requirements is properly architected, designed, and implemented so as not to exceed cost or schedule constraints. It also involves monitoring changes and analyzing the implications these changes may have on the project.

23. How are changes to explainability requirements documented and versioned in the project? For example, is there a document in which the impact of these changes on explainability requirements is analyzed?

If **yes** to question **23** — If documented, what attributes are used to manage changes to explainability requirements?

- Version
- Change date
- Change requester
- Person responsible for the record
- Requirements influenced by the explainability requirement
- Others: _____

Tools

24. Which tools do you use that provide specific support for explainability?

Part 4 – Challenges and Needs

This section aims to identify the challenges, difficulties, and perceived needs related to the inclusion of explainability as a requirement in ML projects.

25. In the project under discussion, was the explainability requirement neglected? If so, how did this impact the project? For example, did it affect system acceptance by users or create difficulties in explaining results to stakeholders?
26. Which quality attributes can be promoted through explainability? Trust, security, transparency, user satisfaction, comprehensibility, usability, ethics, and any others the participant considers relevant.
27. What are the main obstacles to incorporating explainability in ML projects? Possible factors:
- Deliverable quality
 - Project deadlines
 - Team (size, composition, organization)
 - Financial resources
 - Infrastructure
 - Communication with stakeholders
 - Lack of a structured Requirements Engineering process
 - Lack of understanding of what should be delivered as explainable, especially within the development team
 - Other: _____
28. Is explainability still perceived as a cultural issue within the organization?